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PHONETIC STYLISTIC DEVICES

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ANNOTATION

This article deals with the analysis of phonetic stylistic devices and expressive means in the works of poets.

Examples from poetry are given in this research work and they are of great importance for learning stylistics

KEY WORDS: - Stylistics, poetry, phonetic stylistic devices, onomatopoeia, alliteration, rhyme, sound.

I.R.Galperin divides expressive means and stylistic devices into three groups: phonetic, lexical and syntactical. Phonetic expressive means and stylistic devices include onomatopoeia, alliteration, rhyme and rhythm.

Stylistics, a branch of applied linguistics, is the study and interpretation of texts of all types and/or spoken language in regard to their linguistic and tonal style, where style is the particular variety of language used by different individuals and/or in different situations or settings.

What is the purpose of stylistics? Stylistics examines the creativity in the use of language. It enhances the way we think about language and its uses. Thus the stylistic process, examining the creativity of language use, develops our understanding of literature.

Poetry is a type of literature, or artistic writing, that attempts to stir a reader's imagination or emotions. The poet does this by carefully choosing and arranging language for its meaning, sound, and rhythm. Some poems, such as nursery rhymes, are simple and humorous.

Onomatopoeia refers to words that sound exactly or almost exactly like the thing that they represent. Many words that we use for animal or machine noises are onomatopoeia words, such as "moo" for the sound a cow makes and "beep beep" for the noise of a car horn. Words like "slurp," "bang," and "crash" are also onomatopoeia

words. Even some ordinary words like “whisper” and “jingling” are considered onomatopoeia because when we speak them out loud, they make a sound that is similar to the noise that they describe.

Alliteration is the recurrence of an initial consonant sound in two or more words which either follow each other or appear close enough to be noticeable. Functions of alliteration are to consolidate effect, to heighten the general aesthetic effect, to impart a melodic effect to the utterance, emphasis and mnemonic effects. Shel Silverstein frequently used alliteration in his poems for children to create a fanciful tone, even when it meant creating nonsense words. "The Gnome, The Gnat, & The Gnu" repeats the "gn" sound throughout the verse.

I saw an ol' gnome
Take a gknock at a gnat
Who was gnibbling the gnose of his gnu.
I said, "Gnasty gnome,
Gnow, stop doing that.
That gnat ain't done gnothing to you."
He gnodded his gnarled ol' head and said,
"Til gnow I gnever gnew
That gknocking a gnat
In the gnoodle like that
Was gnot a gnice thing to do."

Rhyme is the repetition of identical or similar terminal sound combinations of words. There are two types of rhyme: full rhyme and incomplete rhyme. Dissevering and consolidating are two main functions of rhyme. Rhyme schemes are described using letters of the alphabet, so that each line of verse that corresponds to a specific type of rhyme used in the poem is assigned a letter, beginning with "A." For example, a four-line poem in which the first line rhymes with the third, and the second line

rhymes with the fourth has the rhyme scheme ABAB, as in the lines below from the poem “To Anthea, who may Command him Anything” by Robert Herrick:

Bid me to weep, and I will weep
While I have eyes to see
And having none, yet I will keep
A heart to weep for thee

Rhythm is a flow, movement, procedure, characterized by basically regular recurrence of elements or features, as beat, or accent, in alternation with opposite or different elements or features.

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